

**TWITTER AND INSTAGRAM: AN IMPEDIMENT TO READING
HABITS OF UNDERGRADUATES IN SELECTED PUBLIC
UNIVERSITIES IN NORTH CENTRAL NIGERIA**

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Abstract

The study investigated the influence of Twitter and Instagram usage on reading habits of undergraduates in selected public universities in North Central Nigeria and the place of social media in the society. Two research questions guided the study and two hypotheses were formulated. The study adopted a survey research design. The media equation theory by Byron Reeves and Clifford Nass (1996) claimed that computers tend to be treated like people or human beings. The population for the study comprised 26,320, three hundred (300) level students from seven Federal Universities in North Central Zone of Nigeria. The sample size of three hundred and ninety-four (300) level undergraduates from three federal universities (Federal University of Agriculture, Makurdi, Benue State, Federal University Lafia, Nasarawa State and Federal University, Lokoja, Kogi State) were randomly selected from the seven for the study. Accidental sampling technique was adopted to compose the undergraduates for the study. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire validated by experts. The reliability of the questionnaire was established using Cronbach Alpha method and a reliability coefficient of 0.85 was obtained. Data collected was analyzed using Mean and Standard Deviation to answer the research question and Chi-square Statistic to test the hypotheses at 0.05 significant level. Findings of the study revealed that, Twitter and Instagram usage have negative influence on the reading habits of undergraduates. The study concludes that social media platforms like Twitter and Instagram have led to a decline in the reading habits of Nigerian students in universities. The study recommends that University

institutions should organize seminars on “appropriate use of social media platforms” to stir the interests of their students so as to give themselves more to reading and researching.

Keywords: Social Media, Twitter, Instagram and Reading Habits

Resume

Cet article examine l'influence de l'utilisation de Twitter et d'Instagram sur les étudiants des universités publiques sélectionnées dans la région du nord-centre du Nigéria et la place des médias sociaux dans la société. Deux questions de recherche ont été posées ainsi que deux hypothèses. L'étude a adopté le modèle de recherche par sondage. La théorie de l'équation des médias de Byron Reeves et Clifford Nass (1996) utilisée affirme que les ordinateurs ont tendance d'être traités comme des personnes ou des êtres humains. La population de l'étude comprend 26,320 étudiants en troisième année à l'université dans sept universités fédérales de la région nord-centre du Nigéria. L'échantillon de trois cent quatre-vingt-quatorze étudiants en troisième année universitaire de trois universités fédérales (l'Université fédérale d'agriculture, Makurdi dans l'État de Benue, l'Université fédérale de Lafia, dans l'État de Nasarawa et l'Université fédérale, Lokoja, dans l'État de Kogi) a été choisie au hasard parmi les sept universités pour l'étude. La technique d'échantillonnage accidentel a été adoptée pour constituer les étudiants universitaires pour l'étude. L'instrument de collecte des données était un questionnaire structuré et validé par des experts. La fiabilité du questionnaire a été établie à l'aide de la méthode Cronbach Alpha et un coefficient de fiabilité de 0,85 a été obtenu. Les données collectées ont été analysées à l'aide de la moyenne et de l'écart type pour répondre aux questions de recherche et de la statistique du chi carré pour tester les hypothèses au niveau de la signification de 0,05. Les résultats de l'étude ont révélé que l'utilisation de Twitter et d'Instagram avait une influence négative sur les habitudes de lecture des étudiants universitaires. L'étude conclut que les plateformes de médias sociaux comme Twitter et Instagram ont conduit à une baisse des habitudes de lecture des étudiants nigériens dans les universités. L'étude recommande que les institutions universitaires organisent des ateliers sur «l'utilisation appropriée des plateformes de médias sociaux» pour éveiller les intérêts de leurs étudiants afin de se consacrer davantage à l'étude et à la recherche.

Mots-clés: Médias sociaux, Twitter, Instagram et habitudes de lecture

Introduction

One of the breakthroughs in information and communication technology in the 21st century was the discovery and emergence of the new media (social media) which have facilitated the creation of the different platforms for social

interaction. Social media is new web technology which is recognized and widely used by all internet users (Hussein, 2010). Social media are a collection of Internet websites, services, and practices that support collaboration, community building, participation, and sharing. Nowadays, the users from all over the world are able to communicate co-operatively, share information and take attraction to their shares (Buzzi&Buzzi, 2011). Via social media, users can share not only news but also photos, videos and many other personal moments (Hughes, 2009). Social media platforms motivate their users to create groups, support each other and increase their shares. These technologies have attracted the interest of higher education students and faculty members looking for ways to engage and motivate their students to be more active learners (Hughes 2009). Social media sites, such as Twitter, Instagram, Facebook, Myspace, and WhatsApp among others have become an indispensable part of students' lives (Junco, 2010).

Twitter is one of the most popular social media platforms used among students nowadays. Communication on Twitter can be managed in form of short messages around 140 characters (Grosbeck & Holotescu, 2008). Social network structure of Twitter allows its users to follow each other and communicate via short messages. Twitter allows students to connect with each other and create uninterrupted communication (Dunlap & Lowenthal, 2009). Twitter has the potential of being used as a professional and social networking site since individuals who have similar interests can meet on Twitter (Lucky, 2009). One of the most important aspects is that the communication occurs in real time. This is also stated by Parry (2008) and Young (2008) who suggest that the exchange of information is immediate between peers. Also, users can share information and ideas immediately using Twitter on mobile devices. Research has shown that the number of individuals using Twitter is increasing significantly each day.

Instagram is also one of the most popular social media platforms used among students. It is an online, mobile phone, photo-sharing, video sharing and social networking service that allow users to take pictures and videos and share them on their social media platform (Ting, Ming, Run, &Choo, 2015). Instagram is a popular visual social media site. People share all sorts of stunning visuals of their lives and stories. A recent survey affirmed that Instagram is still the most popular social media network for undergraduate students at the age of 18-24 (NapoleonCat, 2017). Instagram as a fastest growing social media is increasing in popularity more than any other type of social media (Meeker, 2015). With Instagram, young people and specifically teenagers spend a lot of time browsing through other people's photos.

Reading is the cornerstone for lifelong learning by individuals all round development. To have all-round educational development, intensive and

extensive forms of reading cannot be neglected by high school students. Generally, it is a known fact that developing good reading habit is very crucial to students' educational outcomes. According to Owusu-Acheaw (2014), reading habits determine the academic achievements of students. To a great extent it also shapes students' personality and enhance thinking abilities to create new ideas. Thus, the creative abilities would be heightened. Developing good reading habits requires self-discipline on the part of students in the area of time management. In producing all-round development, students in the 21st century should not downplay good reading habits.

In this 21st century, undergraduate students are known to be heavy users of social media. According to Jones (2007) and Young (2004), since undergraduate students are heavy internet users in the aspect of social media, they may be at risk of developing internet related problems as regards their academic activities. Hetting and Knapp (2011) found that social media exerts some negative effects on students' reading habits. As Shabo and Usofia (2009) pointed out, the reading culture of learners has been washed down the drain as a consequence of the evolution of technology and advent of social media. Spending immeasurable hours on social media sites such as Twitter and Instagram can deflect the focus and concentration from a particular task in school like reading habits. Thus, excessive use of these social media networking sites may take most of the time of students and redirects it towards non-constructive, sometimes unethical, deceptive and/or improper activities in school. These social media platforms may increase students' tendency towards non-instructive, unscrupulous and inappropriate activities in the school and takes away their time from reading their books and carrying out researches. Students have been found oftentimes utilizing social media to while away time and for purposes which disengage them from reading in school.

Problem Statement

The use of social media platforms such as Twitter and Instagram affords students and institutions multiple opportunities to improve learning methods. Contrary to this, the researchers have observed that some students have diverted social media usage towards non-educational, unethical and inappropriate actions and behaviours. Some students, instead of taking advantage of the opportunities afforded by social media for enhancing their reading habits and other learning purposes, have shifted their attention to using it for other reasons. Although these social media platforms can potentially increase student learning and reading habits through interactions, it can also impact negatively on students' academic achievements. Also, despite the widespread use of social media particularly Twitter and Instagram by students and its increased use by instructors, very little

empirical evidence is available concerning the influence of Twitter and Instagram usage on students' reading habits. This gap in literature and taking into consideration the observations of the researchers necessitated this study.

Objectives of the Study

The specific objectives of the study are to:

- i. Determine the influence of Twitter usage on reading habits of undergraduates in selected public universities in North-Central Nigeria.
- ii. Determine the effect of Instagram usage on the performance of undergraduate students in selected public universities in North-Central Nigeria.

Research Questions

- i. How does Twitter usage influence undergraduates' reading habits in selected public universities in North Central, Nigeria?
- ii. How does Instagram usage influence undergraduates' reading habits in selected public universities in North Central, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

- i. Twitter usage has no significant influence on undergraduates' reading habits in selected public universities in North Central, Nigeria
- ii. Instagram usage has no significant effect on undergraduate reading habits in selected public universities in North Central, Nigeria

Literature Review

Since the emergence of social media, not much research has been conducted by scholars. However, the few that have been done shall be reviewed in order to ascertain its influence on students reading habits and subsequently performance to give this study a footing. Akande and Oyedepo (2018) conducted a study on effects of social media use on the reading habits of selected high school students in Nigeria. The study found that high school students spend more time using the social media especially with the affordability of smart phones, thereby causing an uncultured lifestyle of reading. The study concluded that, indisputably, it is obvious that the use of social media has wreaked a great havoc on the reading culture of high school students. Schill (2011) believes that the more time students spend on social media platforms like Twitter, the less time they spend reading. Agyekum and Arthur (2018) reported that reading periods get distracted by students' tendencies to access social media platforms like Instagram. The results of a study by Owusu-Acheaw & Larson (2015) showed that the use of social media had affected students' academic work; most of the respondents used social media sites to chat rather than for academic purposes. Dike, Eke and Babarinde (2013) asserted that students use social media extensively, while adults have

become apprehensive about its effect on reading habits of students. In another study of Nigerian students' reading habits, Aina, Ogungbeni, Adigun and Ogundipe (2011), concluded that Nigeria cannot be regarded as a reading nation because the younger generation of Nigerians does not consider reading a leisure activity. Palani (2012) as cited in Owusu-Acheaw (2014) asserted that reading is an essential and important aspect for creating a literate society in the world. However, with the new development of high school students' addiction to social media, this could possibly constitute an inhibition to reading that will enhance effective learning. Mushtaq (2018) investigated the effects of Social Media on the Undergraduate Students' Academic Performances and reported that social media like Twitter influence the academic performance of students negatively, because they distract the students from their studies and that addiction to social media is problematic. A study by Olutola, Olatoye and Olatoye (2016) on "Assessment of Social Media Utilization and Study Habit of Students of Tertiary Institutions in Katsina State" reported that there is significant influence of students' level of social media utilization on their study habit.

Methodology

The study adopted a survey research design. The population for the study comprises 26,320, three hundred (300) level students from seven Federal Universities in North Central zone of Nigeria. The sample size of 394 three hundred level undergraduate students from three federal universities (Federal University of Agriculture, Makurdi, Benue State, Federal University Lafia, Nasarawa State and Federal University, Lokoja, Kogi State) randomly selected from the seven was used for the study. However, sample size of 394 was determined using Yaro Yamane Formula. Accidental sampling technique was adopted to compose the undergraduate students for the study. This is a sampling technique that involves choosing the nearest individuals as respondents and continuing the process until the required sample size is obtained. The sampling technique was employed because, it was impossible for the researcher to identify with all the 300 level students in the sampled universities for random selection, hence only those that the researcher accessed were used for the study. The instrument for data collection was a self-structured questionnaire validated by experts. The reliability of the questionnaire was established using Cronbach Alpha method and a reliability coefficient of 0.83 was obtained. Data for the study was collected by the researchers with the aid of research assistants from the sampled universities. Data collected was analyzed using Mean and Standard Deviation to answer the research questions and Chi-square Statistic to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The benchmark of 2.50 was used to answer the research questions since the response options of the questionnaire was on a four-point rating scale

Results

Research Question 1: How does Twitter usage influence undergraduates' reading habits in selected public universities in North Central, Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation Analysis of the influence of Twitter Usage on habits of undergraduates in North Central Nigeria

S/N	Item Statement	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	SD	Decision
1	I rarely stick to my reading time table in school as a result of twitting.	98	179	75	42	2.84	.92	Agree
2	My reading habit is adversely affected as a result of twitting.	74	180	96	44	2.72	.89	Agree
3	I spend less hours reading compared to the hours I spent reading Twitter posts.	70	181	112	31	2.74	.83	Agree
4	Since I became engaged on Twitter, my reading habit has reduced	69	199	74	52	2.72	.90	Agree
5	Constant reading of Twitter posts is a problematic issue that has affected my reading in school.	80	190	39	85	2.67	.88	Agree
6	Twitter distracts me greatly from reading.	70	191	82	51	2.71	.90	Agree
7	I have the urge to go online "twitter" whenever I am in class to read.	78	168	100	48	2.70	.87	Agree
8	My reading habit has been poor due to twitting.	88	179	100	32	2.85	.87	Agree
9	I spend my productive time in twitting than reading my books.	102	175	63	54	2.82	.96	Agree
10	Twitting has negatively affected my reading hours.	84	189	77	44	2.79	.86	Agree
Cluster Mean and SD						2.76	.89	Agree

Data presented on Table 1 revealed that, the respondents agreed to all the items with mean scores ranging from 2.71 – 2.85 which are above the benchmark of 2.50. The table also revealed close Standard Deviation values ranging from .84 – 1.02 which showed that the respondents were homogeneous in their responses. The grand mean of all the items was revealed to be 2.76 and SD= .89. With this grand mean, it can be deduced from this finding that twitter usage has negative influence on reading habits of undergraduate students in North Central Nigeria.

Research Question 2: How does Instagram usage influence undergraduates' reading habits in selected public universities in North Central, Nigeria?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation Analysis of the influence of Instagram Usage on reading habits of undergraduates in North Central Nigeria

S/N	Item Statement	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	SD	Decision
11	When Instagramming, I barely stick to my timetable in school.	39	221	71	68	2.61	.88	Agree
12	My reading habit is adversely affected by Instagramming.	32	189	112	66	2.50	.83	Agree
13	I spend less hours reading compared to the hours I spent reading Instagram posts.	51	193	88	67	2.60	.91	Agree
14	Since I became engaged on Instagram, my reading habit has depreciated.	62	197	74	61	2.66	.92	Agree
15	Constant Instagram post is a problematic issue that affects my reading habit.	71	164	98	61	2.62	.95	Agree
16	Instagram distracts me greatly from reading my books.	51	178	99	66	2.54	.93	Agree
17	I have the desire to post pictures on “Instagram” whenever I am in class to read.	44	197	92	61	2.57	.88	Agree

18	My reading habit has not improved as a result of discussions I engage in on Instagram.	79	199	68	53	2.80	.92	Agree
19	I share my productive time of reading engaging in Instagramming.	39	221	71	63	2.59	.88	Agree
20	Even if I stop Instagramming, it will not in any way increase my reading hours.	32	107	189	66	2.27	.83	Disagree
Cluster Mean and SD						2.58	.89	Agree

Data presented on Table 2 revealed that, except for item 20 with a Mean of 2.27 and SD =.89, the respondents agreed to other items with mean scores ranging from 2.50 – 2.66 which are above the benchmark of 2.50. The table also revealed close Standard Deviation values ranging from .83 – .95 which showed that the respondents were homogeneous in their responses. The grand mean of all the items was revealed to be 2.58 and SD=.89. With this grand mean, it can be deduced from this finding that Instagram usage has negative influence on reading habits of undergraduate students in North Central Nigeria. The significance of these results will be confirmed by the following test of hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: Twitter usage has no significant influence on undergraduates' reading habits in selected public universities in North Central, Nigeria

Table 3: Chi-Square Test of the Significance of the Influence of Twitter on Reading Habits of Undergraduates

Variables	N	Df	χ^2_{cal}	Sig	Alpha Level	Remark
Twitter Usage						
	394	27	511.224	.000	.05	Significant
Reading Habits						

Df = Degree of Freedom; χ^2_{cal} = Chi-Square Calculated Value; Sig = P-Value

Table 3 shows the Chi-square calculated value of 511.224, degree of freedom $df=27$ and a sig (P-value=0.00) which is less than the alpha value ($\alpha=.05$). Since $P<.05$, the result is significant, therefore the null hypothesis is rejected. This implied that, Twitter usage has significant influence on undergraduate students' reading habits in universities in North Central, Nigeria

Hypothesis 2: Instagram usage has no significant influence on undergraduates' reading habits in selected public universities in North Central, Nigeria

Table 4: Chi-Square Test of the Significance of the Influence of Instagram on Reading Habits of Undergraduates

Variables	N	Df	$\chi^2 cal$	Sig	Alpha Level	Remark
Instagram Usage	394	27	363.901	.000	.05	Significant
Reading Habits						

Df = Degree of Freedom; $\chi^2 cal$ = Chi-Square Calculated Value; Sig = P-Value

Table 4 shows the Chi-square calculated value of 363.901, degree of freedom $df=27$ and a sig (P-value=0.00) which is less than the alpha value ($\alpha=.05$). Since $P<.05$, the result is significant, therefore the null hypothesis is rejected. This implied that, Instagram usage has significant influence on undergraduate students' reading habits in universities in North Central, Nigeria

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study revealed that, Twitter usage has negative influence on undergraduates' reading habits in universities in North Central, Nigeria. Similarly, a test of related hypotheses revealed a significant influence of Twitter usage on undergraduate students' reading habits. The findings corroborate Akande and Oyedepo (2018) who found that high school students spent more time using social media especially with the affordability of smart phones, thereby causing an uncultured lifestyle of reading. The finding is in tandem with that of Mushtaq (2018) who investigated the effects of Social Media on the Undergraduates' Academic Performances and reported that social media like Twitter influence the academic performance of students negatively, because they distract the students from their studies and that addiction to social media is

problematic. The findings also corroborate Olutola, Olatoye and Olatoye (2016) who reported that there is significant influence of students' level of social media utilization on their study habit. This finding as reported could be in the utilization of social media platform like Twitter among students. Similarly, Schill (2011) believes that the more time students spend on social media platforms like twitter, the less time they spend reading. The implication of this finding is that students' study habits (reading) will continue to dwindle as long as they are engaged Twitter which takes a lot of their times off their studies.

The study also revealed that Instagram usage has negative influence on undergraduates' reading habits in universities in North Central, Nigeria. A test of hypothesis of this finding revealed that Twitter usage significantly influences undergraduates' reading habits. This finding agrees with that of Kojo, Agyekum & Arthur (2018) who reported that reading periods get interfered with by students' tendencies to access social media platform like Instagram and this significantly affects their reading habits. The findings also corroborate with the assertion of Dike, Eke and Babarinde (2013) who stated that students use social media extensively, while adults have become apprehensive about its effect on reading habits of students. This could be why Shabo and Usofia (2009) pointed out, that reading culture of learners has been washed down the drain as a consequence of the evolution of technology and advent of social media like the Instagram.

Conclusion

It is the conclusion of this study that the use of social media platforms like Twitter and Instagram has led to a decline in the reading habits of Nigerian students in universities. As confirmed in this study, social media usage has become an issue of increasing concern in education. It is also established that spending more time on social media platforms has become common in exacerbating poor reading habits among university students. The revelation from this study is assumed to serve as a basis for understanding, improving and achieving learning outcomes through appropriate use of social media so as to avoid the possible negative influence on students' reading habits.

Recommendation

Based on the findings of this Study, following recommendations were made;

1. University institutions should organize seminars on appropriate use of Instagram platforms stir the interest of their students so as to give themselves more to reading and researching.
2. Undergraduates must realize all the potential harm excessive use of twitter and Instagram platforms and responsibly approach the learning process to achieve academic result. Students should use all available

online platforms effectively and must be conscious of social Media negative effects and should try as much as possible to create a balance so as not to get carried away while learning.

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